

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Molluscan pests of azolla

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Destruction of azolla by snails poses a serious problem to mass multiplication in India. Snails primarily responsible for azolla loss are:

Lymnaea (Pseudosuccinea) luteola f. *typica* Lamarck. A small and floating snail, common in wet rice fields almost year round. Peak season is July-October. It swims in water and, with the help of its foot, adheres to the rice stem, often above water level. In azolla-

multiplying tanks, it clings firmly and feeds voraciously.

Bellamya bengalensis f. *typica* (Lamarck). A cone-shaped snail found in rice fields and water courses year round. Peak population is in July-September when there are heavy monsoon showers. It often is submerged in wet rice fields and in azolla multiplying tanks.

Pila globosa (Swainson). A big, almost globular snail seen in wet rice fields and water courses almost year round, except in December and January when cold weather sets in and most rice fields become dry. Peak numbers in rice

Rate of feeding on azolla by 3 species of snail in Chinsurah, India.

Snail	Av wt (g) of adult snail (mean of 20 specimens)	Rate of feeding/24 hours per snail (g)
<i>Lymnaea luteola</i>	0.20	0.19
<i>Bellamya bengalensis</i>	2.90	0.33
<i>Pila globosa</i>	34.01	0.98

fields and azolla multiplying tanks are found July-September.

Laboratory experiments determined the rate of feeding on azolla by the three snail species (see table). Room temperature was 21°-26° C. ■

Bird damage on some rice varieties at Aduthurai, India

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Rose-ringed parakeets *Psittacula krameri*, house sparrows *Passer domesticus*, and weaver birds *Ploceus* spp. feed on rice grains from milky stage on. Damage caused by birds was observed during 1981 kharif. Experimental plots were 1 m² with 4 rows of 10 hills each for 16 varieties. Total panicles and damaged panicles were counted on 10 randomly selected hills of each variety and a Standard Evaluation System for Rice damage rating was assigned. The angle of the boot leaf to the panicle was measured.

Twelve varieties had more than 20% damage (see table). IR30 was completely destroyed, Pankaj had no damage. IR20, the most popular variety in the region, had 32.1% damage.

Where the angle between boot leaf and the panicle was narrow, bird damage was less than in varieties having wider angles. The damage was also less in varieties having a boot leaf as long as or slightly longer than the panicle. ■

Bud-damaged panicles on some rice varieties at Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Damaged panicles (%)	Damage rating ^a	Angle of boot leaf to panicle
Pankaj	0.0	0	10-15
IR8	8.7	5	40-60
IR32	10.0	5	10-30
IR48	13.1	5	30-40
IR24	21.9	5	40-60
IR54	26.9	9	40-60
IR20	32.1	9	40-90
IR5	34.2	9	40-90
IR36	41.6	9	40-60
IR52	52.9	9	20-60
IR26	61.0	9	30-50
IR50	63.2	9	40-80
IR40	72.3	9	30-80
IR22	76.2	9	40-90
TNAU20216	90.0	9	80-160
IR30	100.0	9	60-90

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = 26-100%.

ERRATA

Roy, A. K. Effect of sheath blight infection on respiration and transpiration of rice plants. Vol. 7, No. 1 (Feb 1982):

On page 20, line 7 of the middle column should read "increased (difference in manometric)"

Soil and crop management

Effect of surface application of straw on phototrophic nitrogen fixation

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A field experiment during the dry season tested the effect of surface application of straw on phototrophic nitrogen fixation. Continuously flooded study plots had received no N fertilizers for 5 years. Subplots were 1-m × 1-m metal frames inside each experimental plot. IR36 was transplanted at 16 hills/subplot at 20-cm × 20-cm spacing. Weeds were removed as they emerged. Treatments (each with 3 replications) were:

Control: carbofuran added at 3 kg active ingredient/ha every 2 weeks.

Straw treatment: ground straw (0.85% N) applied at 300 g/m² (3 t/ha). Carbofuran applied as in control.

Nitrogen-fixing activity (acetylene